

D5.9 - FAIR-oriented research data management: Support, Training and Assessment Activity Report update

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable reports on the activities and results of Tasks 5.3, Helpdesk, and documentation for promoting FAIR practices and support to FAIR oriented data stewardship, and Task 5.4, Training modules on FAIR oriented research data management tools and solutions, during the second reporting period (January 1st, 2021, to December 31st, 2022). The document provides an update and builds upon the results reported in D5.4

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
F2DS	Federated Data Space
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
JISC	Joint Information Systems Committee
OBO	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
RI	Research Infrastructure

VRE

Virtual Research Environment

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the activities and results of Tasks 5.3, Helpdesk and documentation for promoting FAIR practices and support to FAIR oriented data stewardship, and Task 5.4, Training modules on FAIR oriented research data management tools and solutions, during the reporting period (January 1st, 2021, to December 31st, 2022).

This report provides an overview of the activities and achievements of Tasks 5.3 and 5.4 of the EOSC-Pillar project, and updates the information reported in D5.4.

During the first half of the project, most of T5.3 efforts were dedicated to perform landscape research in order to design and launch a preliminary version of the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue. At the time the catalogue was published, there were still several initiatives that were working towards harmonizing and/or defining standards to describe (RDM) learning resources. We adopted the most advanced metadata schema at the time, knowing that it would likely need to be reviewed throughout the course of the project. In this reporting period, we have followed up these initiatives and updated the metadata schema according to the recently published EOSC Future specifications. Values for the newly added metadata fields have also been updated. Besides, we have continued to populate the catalogue with new entries, engaging with WP6 use cases to increase the number of domain specific content and give visibility to the project results. During the reporting period, significant efforts have been put into promoting the catalogue by organizing and/or attending different (training) events, conferences, etc. This has resulted in a growth of registered users (150 as of 24/11/2022 vs. 48 at the end of 2020) and accesses (143 times on average per month).

Task 5.4 prepared an initial training plan (D5.3) at the beginning of the project, which was severely affected by the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak. An update of the training plan was provided in D5.8. Although the main training topics did not substantially change, the new situation required an adaptation of the training methods and gave the opportunity to focus the training activities on specific communities and collaborate with relevant Research Infrastructures. In total, 21 training events have been organized throughout the project, and additional training material has been produced in relation to WP6 use cases.

1 Introduction

The objective of this deliverable is to report on the activities and results of Tasks 5.3 (Helpdesk and documentation for promoting FAIR practices and support to FAIR-oriented data stewardship) and 5.4 (Training modules on FAIR-oriented research data management tools and solutions).

In D5.4[1], we focused on providing a detailed description about the rationale, design and technical set up of the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue. In this deliverable, we put more emphasis on the work that has been done to engage with related projects with the objective to enhance the interoperability of the catalogue and its alignment with the EOSC future minimal metadata set for the discovery of learning resources.

For Task 5.4, an updated training plan (D5.8[2]) was submitted during the reporting period, which provided an overview of the adaptations made to the training approach in the light of the circumstances set by the COVID-19 pandemic. Therefore, for this deliverable we focus only on providing information about the training events that were performed during the reporting period.

2 Task 5.3: Helpdesk and documentation for promoting FAIR practices and support to FAIR oriented data stewardship

In this section, we will provide an overview of the different activities performed for T5.3. In the first half of the project, most of the effort was put into designing the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue, adding content and promoting it. We also started to engage with relevant projects which were involved in FAIR data stewardship training. This engagement was consolidated in the second half of the project, and has materialized in a series of important outputs: the adaptation of the metadata schema of the catalogue to align with the EOSC Future specifications (Section 2.2.1), the creation of a task force to develop Quality Assurance criteria for catalogues of training materials (Section 2.4.1), and the organization of workshops and training events (Section 3.3 and 3.4) .

2.1 Engagement and cross-collaboration with relevant projects

At earlier stages of the project, we identified several projects and networks that were relevant for Task 5.3. Some of these work on the elaboration of conceptual frameworks for the description and classification of data stewardship competences and/or training material. Others are projects that develop RDM or data stewardship training and even training catalogues. A summary of these initiatives was provided in D5.4. In this section, we detail the activities we have performed in the reporting period to engage with such networks.

2.1.1 Terms4FAIRskills annotate-a-thon: 22, 24 & 26/02/2021

The terms4FAIRskills project[3] aims to create a formalized terminology that describes the competencies, skills and knowledge associated with making and keeping data FAIR. One of the main uses of this ontology would be to facilitate the annotation, discovery and evaluation of FAIR-enabling training materials and resources. As many other projects involved in the development of training catalogues, EOSC-Pillar would benefit from this terminology to describe the training materials in the RDM Training and Support catalogue, to improve the findability of the catalogue content.

The project has been developing the ontology in an iterative process, and has engaged with potential users (e.g., FAIRsFAIR, FAIRsharing, ELIXIR, EOSC-Pillar, the Digital Curation Centre, DANS, CINES and CODATA) during a series of “annotate-a-thons”. The purpose of these events was for participants to actively use the terminology to annotate training materials and provide feedback to terms4FAIRskills so the responsible team can review the terminology, add synonyms, refine the hierarchy and adapt the ontology model.

EOSC-Pillar participated in the “annotate-a-thon” organized during February 2021. The terms4FAIRskills project demonstrated the Semaphora annotation plugin that had been adapted from the EOSC B2NOTE semantic annotation service. This plugin allows users to annotate any

material (i.e. a URL) with the latest version of the terms4FAIRskills terminology to describe online training resources in a user friendly way. It also allows you to make your annotations public, so any user can find materials based on other users' annotations. All participants provided feedback to terms4FAIRskills about both the terminology and the annotation tool.

The availability would allow annotating the training materials in the catalogue with a formalized ontology, enhancing the interoperability and discoverability of the resources. Despite the potential benefits, the ontology is not yet finalized and could not be implemented in the catalogue. Maximizing the catalogue interoperability has been nonetheless an objective within the project, as described in section 2.2. At the moment, the term4FAIRskills project is working to update the ontology to make it conform to the OBO principles (Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology), and to make it available on the OBO Foundry.

2.1.2 EOSC5b-TF/FAIRsFAIR Workshop on Harmonising Training Resource Metadata for EOSC. 14/04/2021

During the previous reporting period (29/10/2020), the EOSC 5b Training Task Force and FAIRsFAIR organized a workshop on interoperability of training resource catalogues[3]. An additional workshop was organized in April 2021 in which EOSC-Pillar was also present. This workshop had the objective to plan a joint action by the current EOSC projects to address the recommendations from the report of the EOSC Working Group on Skills and Training[4], and build upon priority areas identified during the previous workshop held on 29/10/2020.

The report [5] pointed to several initiatives around training catalogues and acknowledged the need for setting the principles and specifications for the federation of EOSC catalogues for learning resources, and provided some initial recommendations for the realization of interoperable catalogues, by providing a minimum metadata application profile based on the worked performed by the RDA Interest Group on Education and Training on handling of research data (RDA ETHRD IG)[6].

Representatives from the EOSC Future project also participated in the meeting and presented the work being done in EOSC Future's WP9 and their proposed scope for a federated training catalogue as part of the EOSC Knowledge Hub.

During the workshop a discussion was organized around three topics: defining a set of minimum metadata elements for learning resources, available metadata schemas and application profiles that could be considered and projects that could be interested in contributing as test cases. A detailed report of the workshop is accessible via Zenodo[7].

2.1.3 OpenAIRE Community of Practice of training coordinators (CoP)

The Community of Practice of Training Coordinators (CoP)[8] is an informal network to share training experiences initiated by a group of people who coordinate training programs of research and e-infrastructures. This initiative of starting a Community of Practice for training coordinators aims, among others, to map out the training activities of various pan-European, EOSC-related initiatives,

to strengthen their training capacity by improved alignment, sharing experiences and good practices, and to initiate cross-infrastructure training activities.

Representatives of EOSC-Pillar Tasks 5.3 and 5.4 have regularly attended the monthly meetings organized by CoP to exchange experiences and best practices around RDM training. The EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue was demonstrated during the meeting on 12/10/2021, with positive feedback received from the community.

Some outcomes from the involvement in the CoP that have an impact on T5.3 were the organization of a workshop about the RDM training & support catalogue landscape during OSFAIR (2.1.5), the creation of a task group to develop quality evaluation criteria and workflows for training catalogues (2.4.1), and the interaction with the EOSC Future project about catalogue specifications (2.1.6, 2.2.1).

2.1.4 RDM training & support catalogue landscape workshop at OSFAIR (20-23/09/2021)

During the summer of 2021, the CoP submitted a proposal to organize a workshop about training catalogues for OSFAIR, to engage the wider community in some of the discussions already started within the EOSC 5b-TF and FAIRsFAIR workshops on catalogue interoperability. The proposal was accepted and the workshop took place on 21/09/2021. As stated in the workshop description page[9], the objectives were to consolidate further steps to improve sustainability of catalogues and their technical and semantic interoperability. The workshop was introduced by short presentations of different relevant initiatives (RDA IG ETHRD, terms4FAIRskills, EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue, the SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit, Dariah Campus, ELIXIR TeSS and EOSC Future), and was followed by interactive discussions about four identified challenges which all different catalogues have to deal with: controlled vocabularies, (meta)data model, curation process and sustainability.

One of the main outcomes of this workshop was to trigger the creation of a task force to elaborate curation guidelines and evaluation criteria for catalogues of training resources, which was further discussed in subsequent CoP meetings (2.4.1). Besides, the different catalogues involved in the workshop were keen to collaborate with the EOSC Future project and establish a method to provide feedback to EOSC Future WP9, discuss how to advance interoperability and ensure the future federation of thematic and project-based catalogues.

A detailed report about the workshop discussions and outcomes was published in an OpenAIRE blog post[10]. The slides of the different presentations are available in Zenodo[11].

2.1.5 EOSC-Pillar as a Pilot for EOSC Future Training Catalogue

One of the objectives within the EOSC Future project was to establish the EOSC Catalogue[12] as a reference point and an aggregator of existing training catalogues. Throughout the catalogue design phase, it was clear that a balance was needed between the number of metadata elements that were needed to ensure the catalogue content quality and reusability versus the threshold required to existing catalogues to onboard their resources.

EOSC Future departed from the metadata set developed by the RDA ETHRD IG and put it to test by engaging with different Pilot Catalogues (EOSC-Pillar, ELIXIR TeSS, SSH Training Discovery Toolkit and DARIAH Campus). A series of meetings were organized to discuss the approach adopted by the existing catalogue and validate the metadata set. The experience showed that the obligation of certain fields of the minimal metadata set was often difficult to fulfill. This led to the definition of two different lists of mandatory fields: a) one for the aggregation of existing resources which favours more recommended fields instead of mandatory ones, b) a second profile for the registration of new resources, with a stricter adoption of the minimal metadata set. The two application profiles are available at the EOSC Future project wiki[13]. At the time of onboarding and in the case where recommended fields are blank, EOSC Future plans to alert providers and encourage them to curate their resources to improve their re-usability.

Since the metadata profile for resource aggregation was decided upon as described above, Task 5.3 started to work in adapting the catalogue metadata profile to align with the EOSC Future specification. This work is further detailed in section 2.2.1.

2.2 Catalogue specifications

The catalogue relies on CKAN technology [14], an open source software that allows to develop and manage open data catalogues. This technology can be extended to support specific communities with the definition of custom metadata profiles [15]. The approach to define the community-specific metadata elements was explained in D5.4. There, it was mentioned that modifications could arise due to work in progress by several relevant projects that are working towards harmonizing and/or defining standards to describe RDM learning resources. In previous sections, we have described the involvement and collaboration of EOSC-Pillar with such projects and initiatives. As previously mentioned, the EOSC Future project recently adopted a set of minimum metadata for the EOSC training resource catalogue, with two different degrees of obligation depending on the resource origin (aggregated vs. newly registered resource).

In the last months of the project, significant effort has been put into mapping and adapting the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue metadata schema to the EOSC Future specification for existing resources and, at a later stage, to update the metadata of existing resources.

2.2.1 Mapping EOSC-Pillar to EOSC Future metadata

When the EOSC Future specifications [13] were released, a mapping between the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue metadata profile and the EOSC Future Minimal Metadata for Learning Resources was performed. For this mapping, we focused on the EOSC Future minimal metadata set for existing resources (for the first harvesting process), which favors recommended fields instead of mandatory, to lower the technical threshold required to ingest existing resources into the EOSC Catalogue. The result of the mapped metadata attributes can be seen in Table 1, where metadata attributes are grouped into different categories.

Table 1 - Mapping between the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue metadata attributes (first column) and the EOSC Future specifications (second column). When one attribute or field has not a direct mapping in one of the projects, this is indicated by a “Not present” value. Attributes which were not present in the EOSC-Pillar catalogue schema, this have been indicated in bold in the EOSC Future column. The EOSC Future definition of each attribute is given in the third column. The last column indicates whether the attribute is mandatory, recommended, or optional in the EOSC Future specification for existing resources.

EOSC-Pillar RMD Training and Support Catalogue	EOSC Future	Definition (EOSC Future)	Mandatory for existing resources?
Basic information			
Title	Title	The human readable name of the learning resource.	Mandatory
URL	URL to Resource	The URL that resolves to the learning resource or to a "landing page" for the resource that contains important contextual information including the direct resolvable link to the resource, if applicable.	Mandatory
Not present	Resource URL Type	The designation of identifier scheme used for the resource URL. It represents the type of the URL of the resource, that is the used scheme (e.g., Web Address URL, DOI, ARK, etc.).	Optional
Author	Author(s)	The name of entity(ies) authoring the resource.	Mandatory
Detailed & access information			
Description	Description	A brief synopsis about or description of the learning resource.	Recommended
Tags	Keyword(s)	The keyword(s) or tag(s) used to describe the resource.	Recommended
License	License	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.	Recommended
Not present	Access Rights	The access status of a resource (e.g. open, restricted, paid).	Recommended
Not present	Version Date	The version date for the most recently published or broadcast resource.	Recommended
Learning information			
Data Type	Learning Resource Type	The predominant type or kind that characterizes the learning resource.	Optional
Target group	Target Group (Audience)	The principal users(s) for which the learning resource was designed	Recommended
Not present	Learning Outcome(s)	The descriptions of what knowledge, skills or abilities students should acquire on completion of the resource.	Recommended
Level	Expertise Level	Target skill level in the topic being taught.	Recommended
Language	Primary	The language in which the resource was	Recommended

	Language	originally published or made available.	
Country	Not present	Country/geographical coverage of the resource	/
Resource format	Format	The predominant format type of the learning resource (e.g. MP4, pdf, scorm, etc.).	Recommended
Not present	Qualification	Identification of certification, accreditation or badge obtain with course or learning resource.	Recommended
Not present	Duration	Approximate or typical time it takes to work with or through the learning resource for the typical intended target audience.	Recommended
Classification information			
Domain	Scientific domain	The branch of science, scientific discipline that is related to the Resource.	Mandatory
Skills group	Not present	High-level categories to group competences	/

In addition to the metadata elements, the controlled vocabularies for the domain field were also revised and adapted. Previously, the EOSC-Pillar RMD Training and Support catalogue used the re3data.org subject classification to populate the domain field, as specified in D5.4. Currently, this field gets its values from the Revised Field of Science and Technology (FOS) Classification in the Frascati Manual by the Working Party of National Experts on Science and Technology Indicators [15], in line with the EOSC Future specifications.

Once the mapping exercise was finalized, the recommended missing metadata attributes were added to the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support metadata profile: Access Rights, Version Date, Learning Outcome(s), Qualification and Duration. These fields were added to the metadata user input form. Besides, the existing records of the “Course” type were reviewed in order to add values to the newly added metadata attributes where information was available (Figure 1). In some cases, training resources lack the recommended metadata fields which would allow users to judge the usefulness that a resource has for them (e.g. learning outcomes, duration. etc), so metadata could not be completed in full for the new fields in all “Course” item catalogues. Finally, the layout of the metadata records was adapted to reflect the different metadata categories (Classification Information, Availability Information, Learning Information, etc).

The technology in which the catalogue relies enables its interoperability with other systems (e.g. DCAT and OAI-PMH) [15]. By including all the mandatory, recommended and optional files of the EOSC Future profile for existing resources and adopting the controlled vocabulary of the domain field, we are also enhancing the syntactic and semantic interoperability with the EOSC Future catalogue. This offers the opportunity for the catalogue to be onboarded in EOSC, increasing the long-term availability of the work that has been done during the project.

Figure 1 - Screenshot showing a catalogue item with the updated metadata schema and with completed values for the newly added metadata attributes.

2.3 Outreach activities

2.3.1 Stories of Data - Podcast

The EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support Catalogue was the main topic of a podcast episode. The goal of this podcast “Stories of Data: Open.Science.Talk”[16] is to make EOSC more tangible for the European research community and to support the implementation of Open Science and FAIR Data. The various episodes present practical examples and introduce some of the EOSC Community’s tools and services. Representatives from the Horizon 2020 project EOSC-Pillar discuss the present and future of EOSC with a focus on EOSC-Pillar contributions, interviewing project partners and guests about all sorts of topics. From the EOSC-Core to services for specific communities, from the vision - to the mission - to the reality.

The episode “EOSC - Let's get practical! Vol. 1”[17] is based on an interview with Inge Van Nieuwerburgh and Paula Oset (Ghent University) that was recorded in fall 2021. The podcast

episode was released some months later and promoted via the EOSC-Pillar website, newsletters of the involved institutions and social media (twitter and LinkedIn).

Episode 03	26 Listens by end of June. 2022	32 Listens by end of Sept. 2022	48 by end of November 2022	https://spotifyanchor-web.app.link/e/JLmfQ683Qtb
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Figure 2 - Screenshots showing the promotion of the podcast episode

2.3.2 International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL 2022)

The International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL) is a yearly event aimed at researchers on Digital Libraries and related topics. The conference focus on three main areas of interest: scholarly communication (e.g. research data, research software, digital experiments, digital libraries), e-science/computationally-intense research (e.g. scientific workflows, Virtual Research Environments, reproducibility) and library, archive and information science (e.g. governance, policies, open access, open science).

The 2022 edition[18] was organized in Padua, Italy. It welcomed submissions on a few different topics including open science and open data. In the case of the short paper track, some of the topics of focus were of interest for the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue: FAIR data and software, Research Data Management, Data and Research Infrastructure, Data Stewardship, etc. A short paper was submitted and accepted[19], and the catalogue was presented on Friday 23rd September, during the Open Science session. The paper summarized the work that had been done to set up the catalogue, the technical implementation, the type of content it contains and how it

can help RDM support professionals in their daily work. It also introduced the existing challenges shared by different training catalogues and how the community is getting organized to tackle them.

2.4 Catalogue content and users

The EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue holds a total of 146 items as of 1/12/2022. The number of records at the time of the publication of D5.4[1] was 77. During the second half of the project, as WP6 progressed, we involved the use case communities in order to suggest and increase the number of discipline specific training resources. A meeting with members of WP6 was organized in November 2021, where the catalogue was presented and demonstrated to the participants. The possibility to use the catalogue as a gateway for the guidelines of their scientific demonstrators was discussed. As a result of this meeting, new domain entries were registered in the catalogue which serve the communities targeted in WP6:

- Defining Procedures and Services to enforce data provenance for thematic communities and beyond[18] as guidelines targeting Materials Science/Nanoscience and Climate Science communities
- EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE - Quick Start for the earth observations community[21]
- das software package[22] for geoscience community

The catalogue has also grown in the number of users and accesses since the last published report. As of 1/12/2022, the number of registered users is 159 (Figure 3). Metadata records are accessible without registration. However, registered users have access to the VRE and the social networking area of the Training and Support component of the EOSC-Pillar F2DS.

The catalogue has been accessed over 4500 times since it was launched, with an average of 143 accesses per month. The accesses follow a seasonal approach, decreasing in the holiday periods and reaching peaks of up to 433 monthly accesses (Figure 4). These peaks tend to correspond with outreach events or activities. For example:

- EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support Catalogue webinar, 12/11/2020 [23]
- FAIRsFAIR, EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Synergy and Ghent University Instructor Training Workshop, 7-11/06/2021 (3.3)
- FAIRsFAIR-CODATA-RDA Data Steward Training Series, 6-10/09/2021 (3.4)
- International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL 2022), 20-23/09/2022 (2.3.2)

Figure 3 – Number of monthly registered users of the RDM Training and Support catalogue since its launch in June 2020.

Figure 4 – Number of monthly accesses to the RDM Training and Support catalogue since its launch in June 2020.

2.4.1 Quality assurance

Quality assurance (QA) was one of the main challenges that was identified through a series of meetings with members of the community of training catalogues (2.1.1, 2.1.3, 2.1.4) and within the OpenAire Community of Practice of Training Coordinators. Curation and quality checking of training materials which are deposited or registered in online catalogues is often a task which is performed by a small group of people within a project, often without visibility and recognition, leaving the process to a great degree of subjectivity. Some projects have developed internal procedures (e.g. SSHOC organizes yearly sprints to review the catalogue content and have developed internal guidelines and documentation. EOSC-Pillar has an embedded user rating system which allows us to

gather information about the usefulness of a resource. But, in general, there is a lack of a systematic approach for quality assurance.

During OSFAIR, this issue was discussed in detail. It was followed up in subsequent CoP meetings and, finally, a task force was set up of which EOSC-Pillar was a member. The task force convened for the first time in March 2022 to discuss and define the scope of the group, what type of final output was desired, and how to move forward. As agreed by the group, the goal of the Training Coordinators’ Community of Practice (CoP) Task Force on “Learning resources quality assurance” is to *design a generic framework and discipline agnostic recommendations for the quality assurance of learning resources and catalogues of learning resources and/or training/learning platforms that contain such resources*[24].

After the first meeting, the TF started collaborating on a document which set the scope of the QA procedures and defined a series of review benchmarks. The QA criteria for learning resources is now in its final version and will be soon published in Zenodo. The QA framework has been developed as a set of self-assessment checklist of criteria, which tackle three different scenarios or personae:

- QA checklist for the creation of learning resources
- QA checklist for the selection of learning resources that will be included into an online training catalogue.
- QA checklist for the creation of metadata records for the selected materials.

The checklists are generic enough to be applicable in many fields and to be adapted to specific use cases. In the case of the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue, the first checklist is not applicable, but the specificities or adaptations for the relevant checklists are provided below.

2.4.1.1 QA checklist for the selection of learning resources

The quality assurance criteria and procedures in this category focus on the quality of the materials to be included, underpinning the main goal, which is to ensure the quality of the platform/catalogue as a whole.

Table 2 - List of generic QA criteria for the selection of learning resources and its adaptation to the RDM Training and Support catalogue.

Generic criteria	EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue specificities
The thematic scope of the resources is in line with the platform’s/catalogue’s thematic scope.	Thematic scope: training materials as well as day-to-day operational resources with the aim to support data stewards and other RDM (research data management), FAIR data (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) and open science actors
The language of the resources is accepted by the platform/catalogue.	All languages accepted

Country of origin is eligible (if applicable/relevant, e.g. legal requirements).	All countries / geographic territories accepted
Learning outcomes are defined.	Recommended criteria. Only applicable for training resources (e.g. type = course). The lack of the definition of learning outcomes does not necessarily relate to the quality of the material.
Where relevant, training methods (workshops, lectures, labs, etc.), delivery methods (classroom training, self-paced course, etc.) and file formats are in line with the platform's policies.	Recommended criteria. Only applicable for training resources (e.g. type = course). Non compliance does not necessarily relate to the quality of the material.
Information about the level of training and qualifications is provided.	Recommended criteria. Only applicable for training resources (e.g. type = course). Non compliance does not necessarily relate to the quality of the material.
(FAIR resources) File formats are in line with the formats accepted by the platform.	All file formats are accepted, open formats are preferred.
(FAIR resources) All mandatory metadata required by the platform are provided.	Mandatory metadata are: Title, Keywords, Metadata creator, Resource type, Domain, Language, Country, Skill, Level, Target audience, Creator, Access Rights, Version date
(FAIR resources) PIDs (persistent identifiers) are assigned.	Recommended criteria. Resources with a PID are preferred, but this criteria is often difficult to fulfill.
(FAIR resources) Licence information is available.	Recommended criteria. Resources with a clear (open) licence are preferred, but this criteria is often difficult to fulfill.
(FAIR resources) Copyright, usage conditions, access constraints and licensing are declared and all sources are credited in case existing materials are reused.	NA
The origin/provenance of the materials is known and is acceptable for the platform.	The origin of the resources are generally: research performing organizations, public institutions, (European) projects.
User guidelines for the materials are provided.	Recommended criteria.
Responsibilities for the materials are defined (who created, who will maintain and update).	Recommended criteria.
For the catalogues of learning resources that contain only metadata records: Preservation is ensured (e.g. materials are deposited in a repository/platform that can ensure that they are accessible for a reasonable period of time, preferably in repositories with a long-term preservation policy).	All metadata records are assigned a persistent URL, as well as a link to the original resource.

2.4.1.2 QA checklist for metadata records creation

The quality assurance criteria in this category focus on the quality of the metadata records in the platform/catalogue, where the main goal is to ensure the quality of the platform/catalogue and the findability and re-usability of the resources hosted in it.

Table 3 - List of generic QA criteria for metadata records creation and its adaptation to the RDM Training and Support catalogue.

Generic criteria	EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue specificities
The metadata are aligned with the metadata standard used by the platform.	NA. Metadata are manually gathered by the EOSC-Pillar catalogue curators.
The metadata are correct and complete.	All mandatory fields contain information.
Links are valid and accessible.	All metadata records are assigned a persistent URL. Links to original resources are checked by curators.
Quality of media objects is good.	NA
Licences and access rights are appropriate.	Checked by curators, in accordance to the licenses criteria specified in Table 2.
Formats are interoperable.	Catalogue relies on CKAN and (meta)data is interoperable with other systems (e.g. DCAT and OAI-PMH).
Revision procedures are in place (for records).	Metadata records are reviewed by curators.

3 Task 5.4: Training modules on FAIR oriented research data management tools and solutions

The following section reports on the activities of Task 5.4. Deliverable 5.4 provided a summary table of the training plan and summarized how the training strategy had to be adapted due to the COVID-19 pandemic. An update of the training plan with the adaptation approach that was followed was then provided in D5.8[2]. Here, we detail the training activities that have been performed during this reporting period.

3.1 Training courses at Research Performing organizations

Training courses were delivered targeting Research Performing Organisation personnel with different roles (Researchers, Research support staff, ...) and at different career stages (PhD students, senior researchers, etc.).

3.1.1 Research data management in the social sciences (9-3-2021)

This course was organized by the University of Vienna and tackled how social science research practice can benefit from good data management. The event started with an introduction to the most important RDM topics and then focused on how this applies to everyday research. Using several examples from qualitative and quantitative fields, DMPs were presented as a useful tool throughout the research cycle.

- Course information: <https://forschungsdaten.at/en/fair-data-austria/materials/dmps-in-social-sciences/>
- Course material:
 - <https://hdl.handle.net/11353/10.1168878>
 - <https://hdl.handle.net/11353/10.1169818>
- Number of attendees: 97

3.1.2 Open Science and Research Data Management in the Humanities and Cultural Heritage Sciences (20/05/2021-09/06/2021)

This course, designed over nine modules, was intended for researchers working in the humanities and cultural heritage sectors. The course was organised involving the main ESFRI Research Infrastructures working in the field and was dedicated to the National Research Council of Italy (CNR) affiliated. EOSC-Pillar organised the course together with ESFRI Research Infrastructure OPERAS and ICDI, the Italian National Initiative to coordinate efforts to participate in the EOSC. Other RIs and projects involved were: Clarin Eric, Dariah, E-rihs and Ariadne+ and Parthenos. The aim was to introduce and motivate open science and FAIR research data management practices specifically for the domains covered. The course was made by four modules that introduces the basic principles of OS and FAIR RDM, followed by 5 modules where the RIs and projects invited presented specific activities and tools for their target communities. A total of 70 people from CNR

Institutes working in the humanities and cultural heritage sciences attended the course that also relied on a dedicated Virtual Research Environment.

- Event page: <https://www.cnr.it/it/evento/17272/scienza-aperta-e-gestione-dei-dati-per-le-scienze-umane-e-del-patrimonio-culturale-corso-di-formazione>
- Presentations available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/5497914#.YpnoAqhBxaQ>
- Number of attendees: 70

3.1.3 HERCULES Specialized Course 2021, Open Science training session (09/06/2021)

The HERCULES Specialized Course (HSC) is an extensive training that is being organized since 2006, taking place after the main HERCULES School, and combining both theoretical and practical sessions. The 2021 edition took place online from 31st May to 9th June 2021 and was organised by CERIC-ERIC, in the framework of the H2020 projects ACCELERATE and CALIPSOplus and the CEI cooperation fund. The event, open to researchers around the world, is primarily intended for young researchers (PhD students and postdocs) of physics, chemistry and biology, but more experienced researchers interested in the topic can also apply. The session on Open Science was organised by EOOSC-Pillar and OpenAIRE Advance projects to cover main aspects of motivations, Open Science in Horizon Europe and Open Research Europe.

- Course website: <https://www.ceric-eric.eu/events/hercules-specialized-course-2021-the-multi-technique-approach-of-ceric-eric-as-a-tool-for-nanoscience/>
- Presentation available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/4954838#.YpnojahBxaQ>
- Number of attendees: 30

3.1.4 iCARE-2 Research Integrity Course (24/06/2021)

A 4 hrs course organised by iCARE-2 on research integrity; within the course, that targeted young and senior researchers at various Universities linked to iCARE-2 project Open Science principles and Research Integrity aspects were presented by EOSC-Pillar in collaboration with the OpenAIRE-Advance project.

- Presentation available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/5075260#.YQQfvY4zZaQ>
- Number of attendees: 40

3.1.5 Open Science in Research Projects - University of Siena (5-11/11/2021)

The 9 hours course was designed and delivered in three modules for the University of Siena, Italy. The target group was the personnel of the university. The course tackled principal aspects of Open Science and FAIR Research data management in EC funded projects.

- Presentations available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/6412061#.YpozWahBxaQ>
- Number of attendees: 40

3.1.6 Open Science and Research Data Management, Scuola Normale Superiore (15-24/11/2021)

The course was realised within the Transversal Activities at Scuola Normale Superiore.

- Course information and programme: https://www.sns.it/sites/default/files/2021-11/OSRDM_web_2021_0.pdf
- Presentations available at: https://zenodo.org/record/6324828#.Ypo7_6hBw2w
- Number of attendees: 30

3.1.7 Practical course on FAIR Data Stewardship in Life Science (2-11/03/2022)

EOSC-Pillar continued the design and delivery of training for researchers belonging to a specific research community in collaboration with ELIXIR.

A course on FAIR Data Stewardship in Life Science was organised by the EOSC-Pillar project, ELIXIR Italy, the ICDI Competence Centre, and EOSC-Life, in collaboration with ELIXIR Netherlands. The course focused on FAIR data management and stewardship. It provided the skills, tools and standards required to embed Open Science in the research workflow, covering many aspects, such as: Open Science in Horizon Europe, Open Access in publishing, Research Data Management (RDM), FAIR principles, Open Data, and Data Management Plan. The course was structured in 5 on-line training modules, each one built on frontal lessons and several interactions.

25 candidates were selected based on their need for the course as emerging from the application form, where candidates had to describe a research project for which they needed to develop a DMP, and the relevance of the course objectives to their work. In the selection process, priority was given to candidates from ELIXIR-IT member institutions.

At the end of the course, each candidate had to draft a DMP for his/her project to test the competencies acquired in a real set environment.

- Event page: <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/practical-course-fair-data-stewardship-life-science>
- Material available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/6323375#.YppQ1ahBxaQ>
- Number of attendees: 25

3.1.8 Research Data Management: practical course - Ghent University (18/10/2022, 21/10/2022, 25/10/2022, 10/11/2022, 15/11/2022)

These courses on Research Data Management and Open Science were prepared in the context for Ghent University PhD students, in collaboration with the Doctoral Schools programme. Courses on RDM for the Doctoral Schools had been realized in the past but the content was renewed to give a larger emphasis on Open Science and FAIR data practices and tools, as well as to provide more domain-specific material. There were a total of five courses organized, one for each Ghent University faculty cluster: Arts, Humanities and Law, Social and Behavioural Sciences, Life Sciences and Medicine, (Bioscience) Engineering and Natural Sciences. All the material, including interactive hands-on and quizzes, was made openly accessible in the Open Science Framework.

- Course website and materials: <https://osf.io/gdq93/wiki/home/>
- Number of attendees: 97 (for the five courses)

3.2 FAIRsFAIR, EOSC-Pillar, EOSC-Synergy and Ghent University Instructor Training Workshop

During June 2021 (7-11/06/2021), FAIRsFAIR, EOSC-Pillar, EOSC Synergy and Ghent University delivered a three day train-the-trainer workshop [25] to support the development of data stewardship skills among staff in universities and other research institutions in Belgium. A key aim of this workshop was to empower a network of peers where best practices are exchanged and where those with more experience can share their knowledge with those just getting started. The main target audience was data stewards and RDM support staff in Belgium, and the event gathered 30 participants from the emerging community in the country.

The workshop combined a series of theoretical and practical sessions, where participants were given the opportunity to interact and get to know other colleagues in their professional network and exchange their experience in supporting researchers with RDM. Participants were also introduced to key concepts of pedagogy and were able to put these in practice with a course design and development activity. They also got to evaluate their existing training offer and materials, and to explore other potential open training resources that could help them achieve their training goals. Finally, other sessions allowed participants to reflect on their own role as data stewards and on the status of RDM services in their respective institutions.

The EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue was demonstrated during one of the sessions and was incorporated in one of the interactive exercises where participants had to find existing learning materials appropriate for a course they had previously designed. We took the opportunity to gather feedback about the catalogue. Participants who were not aware of the catalogue found it

a valuable resource to plan future training, found the catalogue easy to use and the resources that it contains useful at first glance. After the event, a blog post[26] was published.

3.3 FAIRsFAIR-CODATA-RDA Data Steward Training Series

The CODATA-RDA Schools instructors together with FAIRsFAIR, EOSC-Pillar, EOSC Synergy and Gdańsk University of Technology Library and the Open Science Competence Center, delivered a three day train-the-trainer workshop[27], from 6th to 10th September 2021. The approach of this workshop was similar to the one described in 3.3, although the main target audience in this case were members of staff at the Gdańsk University of Technology, with the objective to support the development of data stewardship skills. In this occasion, the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support catalogue was once again presented and demonstrated to participants, offering it as a tool that can be used in the development of training as part of their RDM support tasks. A detailed blog post[28] was also published after the event, summarising the main outcomes.

3.4 Training material on EOSC services

One of the topics covered by the training programme are EOSC services. The emphasis has been put on services based on the EOSC-Pillar countries and/or services resulting from the EOSC-Pillar technical WPs, but it also includes training related to onboarding services to EOSC. In this line, the project has organized a series of webinars and produced additional training material, in collaboration with the relevant WPs and EOSC-related projects. Webinar recordings and video tutorials and demos are available in the EOSC-Pillar Youtube channel.

- Use case 1 - Procedures and services to enforce data provenance for thematic communities and beyond
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uV-Gi2pouOw>
- Use case 2 - Agile FAIR data for environment and earth system communities
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=D8JsFpjflv0>
- Use case 3 - Integration of data repositories into EOSC based on communities approaches
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iaiFHpj2HgQ>
- Use case 4 - Software source code preservation, reference and access
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QrgAsRXWtKE>
- Use case 5 - Proof of Concept to link HAL publications and NAKALA repository:
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DxZ8H0Q0vHU>
- Use case 6 - Reference data through existing computing services for the bioinformatics community
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WZey8XrCp1I>
- EOSC-Pillar Use case 6 demo – Galaxy
 - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SK9C_MWz6Yk
- Use case 7 - Suitable data formats for seismological big data provisioning via web services
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=57kkGkw8-mA>

- Use case 8 - Definition of big datasets at seismological data centres based on RDA recommendations
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4Oso80i9rME>
- Use case 9 - Integrating heterogeneous data on cultural heritage
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0NBHT2f5Vqk>
- Workshop: Incorporating National and Thematic Service and Resource Catalogues into the EOOSC
 - Intro: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ipL5TQWzMEg>
 - Policy breakout: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1lklofKyswM>
 - Technical breakout: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9DQYrLgU3-A>
 - Wrap-up: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Tv1hBPP_ZbY
- SSH tools for fairification of data in mass
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hygpiLsCJMY>
- SSH tools (Cidoc CRM) for archaeologists to store and expose data (CIDOC CRM Ontology for sharing archaeological data)
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0ZF34982h-M>
- SSH tools for annotation in Linguistics (The ELAN Software for social sciences and humanities):
 - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AiJDOSAzL_I&list=PL700ENAs2ZbLQesxNi3q5nA4m1aH1gz0g
- SSH tools for FAIRification: Share, publish and enhance your scientific data with Nakala (identified in MS25 [27])
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=haMpOdYQGdA&list=PL700ENAs2ZbLQesxNi3q5nA4m1aH1gz0g&index=4>

4 Final remarks

Some of the challenges addressed by the EOSC-Pillar project are to narrow the existing skills gap, as well as to promote a cultural change to realize the EOSC. The European Commission is working towards a research culture in which open science becomes the standard way of working within the European research community. Additionally, EOSC-Pillar seeks to promote FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) data culture and good practices. The work performed in Tasks 5.3 and T5.4 is framed within these objectives by both designing and delivering training on Open Science, RDM and FAIR related topics, as well as by offering a central point for the discovery of training and support materials for those who have a role in advancing (FAIR) data stewardship.

Throughout the course of the project, we were able to deliver more than 20 training events, covering different topics: EOSC Basics, FAIR data principles, Data Stewardship, Research Data Management, EOSC Services, Open Science and EOSC policies, Open Access. Despite the fact that the COVID-19 outbreak had a significant impact in the original training plan, it also gave the opportunity to reach wider (online) audiences and to target specific communities and collaborate with relevant Research Infrastructures who provide FAIR domain services. The RDM Training and Support catalogue was successfully launched and has since grown in the number of resources (146), registered users (150) and accesses (143 on average per month). More recently, the technical specifications were revised in order to align with the EOSC Future catalogue requirements, and the metadata of several entries was updated for an improved re-usability of the resources. The catalogue will be accessible for at least two years after the end of the project. Besides, the technology in which the catalogue relies, in addition to the work that has been done towards enhancing the interoperability of the catalogue, opens up the opportunity to be onboarded onto EOSC. This will be essential to guarantee that the catalogue resources remain accessible in the future, increasing the long term impact of the work done during the project. Synergies were created within the two tasks by: 1) incorporating the training material produced by EOSC-Pillar in the catalogue and, 2) organizing Train the trainer events for data stewards where the catalogue was a source for the reuse of learning resources. Both with the organized training sessions as well as the catalogue, offering a selection of curated and searchable training and support resources about FAIR, open science and research data management (RDM), we have contributed to advance knowledge and skills and to promote good practices within different relevant stakeholders within the EOSC-Pillar community (including those targeted by the WP6 use cases) and the wider European research community.

5 References

- [1] Oset Garcia, Paula, Lazzeri, Emma, Van Nieuwerburgh, Inge, von Hartrott, Philipp, and Geistberger, Julia, “EOSC-Pillar D5.4 FAIR-oriented research data management Support Training and Assessment Activity Report,” Jan. 2021, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.5513882.
- [2] Lazzeri, Emma *et al.*, “EOSC-Pillar D5.8 Training Plan Update,” Apr. 2021, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.5513834.
- [3] “terms4FAIRskills,” *terms4FAIRskills.github.io*. <https://terms4fairskills.github.io/> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [4] “EOSC Skills WG Blogs | EOSC Secretariat.” <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-skills-wg-blogs> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [5] European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. and EOSC Executive Board., *Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science: report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group*. LU: Publications Office, 2021. Accessed: Mar. 15, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>
- [6] “ETHRD-IG Focus Group Materials,” RDA, Sep. 30, 2020. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/education-and-training-handling-research-data-ig/wiki/ethrd-ig-focus-group-materials> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [7] Newbold, Elizabeth, Kayumbi, Gabin, Whyte, Angus, and Lazzeri, Emma, “Summary Report: Workshop on Harmonising Training Resource Metadata for EOSC Communities,” May 2021, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.4769467.
- [8] A. Vieira, “Community of Practice for training coordinators,” *OpenAIRE*. <https://www.openaire.eu/cop-training> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [9] “OSFair - the-rdm-training-support-catalogue-landscape.” <https://www.opensciencefair.eu/2021/workshops/the-rdm-training-support-catalogue-landscape> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [10] “The RDM Training & Support Catalogue Landscape,” *OpenAIRE*. <https://www.openaire.eu/blogs/the-rdm-training-support-catalogue-landscape> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [11] E. Leenarts *et al.*, “OSF workshop resources RDM training and support catalogues (21 September 2021),” Sep. 2021, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.5564865.
- [12] “EOSC Search Service.” https://search.eosc-portal.eu/search/training?q=* (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [13] “Training Catalogue - Minimal Metadata for Learning Resources - EOSC Future Public - Wiki EOSC Future.” <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/Training+Catalogue++Minimal+Metadata+for+Learning+Resources> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [14] “CKAN Homepage.” <https://ckan.org/>

- [15] Candela, Leonardo, Frosini, Luca, Le Franc, Yann, Mangiacrapa, Francesco, and Cazenave, Nicolas, "EOSC-Pillar D5.2 FAIR Research Data Management Workbench Operation Report," Feb. 2021, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.6341732.
- [16] "Revised Field Of Science And Technology (FOS) Classification in the Frascati Manual." DIRECTORATE FOR SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND INDUSTRY COMMITTEE FOR SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGICAL POLICY. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oecd.org/science/inno/38235147.pdf>
- [17] "Stories of Data: Open.Science.Talk," *EOSC-Pillar*, Apr. 19, 2022. <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/stories-data-open-science-podcast> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [18] "EOSC - Let's get practical! Vol. 1 by Stories of Data - Open.Science.Talk." <https://anchor.fm/eosc-pillar/episodes/EOSC---Lets-get-practical--Vol--1-e1i0m89> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [19] "TPDL 2022 Conference Venues," *Google My Maps*, 2007. <https://www.google.com/maps/d/viewer?mid=1oIVHp1h0SILAK6nFx1wvkcPBGPLXLkrK> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [20] P. O. Garcia, L. Berberi, L. Candela, I. Van Nieuwerburgh, E. Lazzeri, and M. Czuray, "Developing the EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support Catalogue," in *Linking Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries*, vol. 13541, G. Silvello, O. Corcho, P. Manghi, G. M. Di Nunzio, K. Golub, N. Ferro, and A. Poggi, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022, pp. 274–281. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-16802-4_22.
- [21] "UC1 Guidelines for researchers: Defining Procedures and Services to enforce data provenance for thematic communities and beyond - EOSC-pillar Catalogue." https://ckan-eoscpillar.d4science.org//dataset/uc1_guidelines_for_researchers_defining_procedures_and_services_to_enforce_data_provenance_for_them (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [22] "EOSCPillar4EarthScience VRE - Quick Start - EOSC-pillar Catalogue." https://ckan-eoscpillar.d4science.org//dataset/eoscpillar4earthscience_vre_-_quick_start (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [23] "dastools SW package - EOSC-pillar Catalogue." https://ckan-eoscpillar.d4science.org//dataset/dastools_sw_package (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [24] "WEBINAR: EOSC-Pillar RDM Training and Support Catalogue | EOSC-Pillar." <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-eosc-pillar-rdm-training-and-support-catalogue> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [25] "Quality assurance criteria - Google Docs." <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1oNB5HL-QqDUKVYFfp5LdXhYWxynFsK3Ax1Q4Gov8w/edit#heading=h.z4cb9gmq81ec> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).
- [26] "Instructor training - Online workshop | EOSC-Pillar." <https://eosc-pillar.eu/events/instructor-training-online-workshop> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).

[27] “Data Stewardship Training - Belgium,” *FAIRsFAIR*, Jul. 07, 2021. <https://www.fairsfair.eu/articles-publications/data-stewardship-training-belgium> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).

[28] “FAIRsFAIR-CODATA-RDA Data Steward Training Series,” *FAIRsFAIR*, Aug. 06, 2021. <https://www.fairsfair.eu/events/training/fairsfair-codata-rda-data-steward-training-series> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).

[29] “FAIRsFAIR-CODATA-RDA Data Steward Training Series - Poland,” *FAIRsFAIR*, Sep. 28, 2021. <https://www.fairsfair.eu/articles-publications/fairsfair-codata-rda-data-steward-training-series-poland> (accessed Dec. 01, 2022).